

STUDY THE ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN PUNE DISTRICT

Dr. Archana Sanjay Desai

Abstract-

Education is one of the most effective force that can save our besieged environment. Environmental Ethics is the scientific study of various issues related to the rights of individual on the environment. It is the moral relationship of human beings with the environment. Students of Standard XI, studying in the higher secondary school in Pune. Secondary school students were taken as the sample for the present study. The size of the sample is 800. It is found that the higher secondary students have high environmental ethics. The girls have high environmental ethics than the boys; the higher secondary students from urban areas have higher environmental ethics than the students from rural areas; the higher secondary students from the private schools have higher environmental ethics than the students from government schools. The higher secondary students residing in rented houses have higher Environmental Ethics than the students residing in their own houses.

Introduction-

Environmental Ethics is the scientific study of various issues related to the rights of individual on the environment. It is the moral relationship of human beings with the environment. It is concerned with the do's and don'ts of human beings with regard to the environment. It deals with ecological rights of all creature present today as well as those, which will follow on the earth. Ethical standards are necessary for long-term conservation and maintenance of nature and its resources. Environmental Ethics refers to the responsibility of understanding the environmental consequences of our consumption, and the need to recognize our individual and social responsibility to conserve natural resources and protect the earth for future generations.

Need for the Study-

Education is one of the most effective forces that can save our besieged environment. The basis of a healthy environment is pure air, pure water and fertile soil. These basic building blocks of life are obviously essential for life to continue and must be cared for, preserved and enhanced. No programme can be a success without education, as education is what makes people aware of the need for any activity and can generate much needed support for that activity.

Environmental Education should develop environmental ethics among the higher secondary students. An environmental approach and an urge to inculcate the responsibility to sustain and maintain the nature become an important task among higher secondary students. In order to develop the value-based environmental society, Environmental Ethics must be promoted among the students. At present various activities are provided in the schools to preserve the environment. Through informal modes like radio, television, newspaper, Internet etc. the importance of environment for human life can be inculcated in the people at large.

This study attempts to investigate the Environmental Ethics of higher secondary school students. It aims at offering meaningful suggestions for improving the Environmental Ethics among the higher secondary school students.

Objectives-

The following objectives were formulated for the present study.

- To find out the Environmental Ethics of higher secondary school students in Pune District.
- To find out the significant difference in the Environmental Ethics of
 - Boys and girls.
 - Urban and Rural Higher Secondary School Students
 - Government and Private School Students
 - Students residing in Own Houses and Rented Houses.

Methodology-

The method used for this study in descriptive survey method.

Sample-

Students of Standard XI, studying in the higher secondary school in Pune District are taken as the sample. The size of the sample is 800. Random sampling technique is used.

Tool-

A Likert-type Pollution Scale is constructed and validated by the investigator to measure the Environmental Ethics. The tool consists of 45 statements, which include positive and negative statements, set against a three-point scale i.e. I agree absolutely, I slightly agree, I don't agree.

Scoring Procedure-

The Environmental Ethics Scale was administered on a random sample of (800) eight hundred students. The subjects were asked to respond to the items marking any one of the three options. I agree absolutely gets 3 marks, I slightly agree gets 2 marks, and I don't agree 1 mark. The summated score of the Environmental Ethics Scale was thus found out for each individual. As there were 45 items in the tool, the maximum score one can get is 135.

Analysis of Data-

From table1, the entire sample had a Mean score of 101.22 and the Standard Deviation of 16.48. The maximum possible score one can get is 135. The Mean score for the entire sample was much higher than the midpoint 67.5. It was found that the higher secondary students have high Environmental Ethics.

Table-1: Mean and 't' values for the Environmental Ethics of Higher Secondary Students

Sr.no	Categories	Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't'	Significance of 0.05 level
1	Entire sample		800	101.22	16.48		
2	Gender	Boy	423	100.79	15.57	0.769	Not Significant
		Girls	377	101.70	17.45		
3	Locality	Urban	400	101.64	15.96	0.716	Not Significant
		Rural	400	100.80	16.99		
4	Management	Government	400	96.96	19.90	7.567	Significant
		Private	400	105.48	14.89		
5	Ownership of House	Own	652	100.18	16.67	4.055	Significant
		Rental	148	105.79	14.81		

It can be also inferred from Table 1 that among the sub-variables the girls have higher Environmental Ethics than the boys; the higher secondary students from urban areas have higher Environmental Ethics than the students from rural areas; the higher secondary students from the private schools have higher Environmental Ethics than the students from government schools. The higher secondary students residing in rented houses have higher Environmental Ethics than the students residing in own houses. The 't' test, in respect of Environmental Ethics at 0.05 level of significance has been found (Table- 1) for sub-sample and the following findings have been made-

- i) Boys and girls do not differ significantly in Environmental Ethics ('t' value 0.769).
- ii) Higher secondary students from the urban areas and rural areas do not differ significantly in Environmental Ethics ('t' value = 0.716).
- iii) Higher secondary students in the government schools and private schools differ significantly in Environmental Ethics ('t' value = 7.567).
- iv) Higher secondary students residing in own houses and in rented houses differ significantly in Environmental Ethics ('t' value = 4.055)

Recommendations-

Educational programmes that promote a sustainable ethical code among boys need to be encouraged and more leadership opportunities must be provided to higher secondary boy students to promote Environmental Ethics among them. Rural higher secondary school students lack Environmental Ethics due to unawareness and unnoticed approaches towards the environment. Private school students show better Environmental Ethics than government higher secondary students due to the varied environmental programmes and opportunities provided to them. Therefore, government higher secondary students should also be encouraged to participate and involve in the environmental programmes that will emulate the love for environment in which of s/he lives. The authorities of government higher secondary schools should take keen interest in implementing suitable activities and enforce rules that will inculcate a satisfactory code of Environmental Ethics. Students who reside in rented houses show higher Environmental Ethics than students who reside in their own houses. This is due to the varied opportunities that they get in the rented houses. Therefore better programmes will stimulate Environmental Ethics among students who reside in their own houses.

References-

- Casey, M. (2007). Millions face hunger from climate change. New York: The Associated Press, April 10.
- Duncan C. Stewart & Taylor N. Johnson - 2018 - Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism 76 (4):441-4
- Norton. B (1984), Environmental Ethic, 6, 131-148
- Rendy. L (1996), Environmental Ethics: “ Nature as Polis”
- Robin Attfield (2006) “The Shape of a globe ethics philosophy social criticism, Jan 2006; 32 : 5-19